

BIODT

biodiversitydigitaltwin

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D7.1 - First Stage Community Platform Integration Report

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Glossary of Terms

Item	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Interface
API	Application Programming Interface
DDI	Distributed Data Infrastructure
DT	Digital Twin
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High Performance Computing
pDT	Prototype Digital Twin
PI	Principal Investigator
WP	Work Package

Keywords

Biodiversity, Digital Twin, Modelling, Simulation, Prediction, High Performance Computing, Integration

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Executive Summary

This Deliverable contains information about the process and work done in creation of services to increase the adoption of solutions developed in the BioDT project. The first section contains general information about decisions regarding community platforms and how to best approach the integration of such services. The second section describes how Puhuri, HEAppE, and the LEXIS Platform are being integrated to enable easy access to HPC services and facilitate the onboarding of BioDT users. The third section focuses on the r4lexis R package, which can be used to enable the execution of LEXIS workflows. This is an important part of the BioDT solution, as it will make it possible for biodiversity researchers and developers to use R to execute BioDT workflows. The fourth section describes work on the R Shiny web application, which will serve as a graphical user interface to interact with the biodiversity prototype digital twins developed in BioDT.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Analysis of possibilities for integration

Establishing several ways for the wider public to access BioDT services is considered essential to maximising the impact of activities undertaken in the project, with this work also involving the possibility of creating integrations to externally developed platforms at a later stage. When considering how end-users will interact with the prototype digital twins (pDT) developed in BioDT, providing independent graphical user interfaces (GUI) was rapidly identified as a common requirement.

To construct custom GUIs for more than eight pDTs during the project lifetime, it also became clear that a shared technical solution is needed. It was proposed that the [R Shiny](#) interface could be used as a common basis for the interfaces, while making it possible to create a separate independent module for each pDT. An additional advantage of this approach is that many partners involved in the BioDT project are knowledgeable about the R language, and some also about R Shiny. The R language is also commonly used by researchers within the biological and environmental sciences. Another advantage of this solution is having a common entry point to multiple pDTs and the possibility for anybody to deploy their own instance, once the source code is made public. Simultaneously, if the R Shiny application is not flexible enough for any of the pDTs, there is a possibility to create a separate pDT-specific custom GUI.

In the meantime, work on the integration of services for user and project management (Puhuri), HPC-as-a-Service middleware (HEAppE) and a federated workflow execution platform (LEXIS Platform) has commenced. This is being pursued to facilitate easier work with account management, computational project management, and the execution of jobs on high performance computing (HPC) clusters, alongside with the possibility to create high level workflows combining cloud and HPC tasks. The service integration work enables pDT development teams to smoothly use the infrastructure services provided, allowing them to concentrate on modelling and hiding from them unnecessary complexity of deploying and running their pDTs. Here, it is important to note that while at the beginning of the project these tools were foreseen as external helper services, later they became part of the BioDT technical infrastructure. As such, work on their integration (including integration with LUMI) is also being pursued as part of activities focused on implementing the BioDT technical platform.

Developments in the project also affected design decisions made in relation to the Shiny web app for BioDT, with it becoming clear that an R package would be needed to be implemented to enable communication with the LEXIS Platform, in particular to enable data transfers between the LEXIS Distributed Data Infrastructure (DDI) and the Shiny web app. It was established that this package should allow one to login into the LEXIS Platform and execute BioDT workflows on the BioDT infrastructure. An advantage of such a package is the ability to create custom R scripts for communicating with the BioDT infrastructure using the LEXIS API, therefore comprising a central point for pDT developers to manage workflows, models and datasets.

1.2 Proposed roadmap

Based on the events described in the previous section, we decided on a rough roadmap in which we prioritised the creation of the `r4lexis` package and the Shiny web application for BioDT. These were needed to deploy the first prototype digital twin (detailed in BioDT Milestone 15) and for the development of pDT GUIs. Following deployment of the first pDT, more attention will be given to other pDTs and their GUIs. We will also further explore whether there are other platforms where we can directly integrate BioDT digital twins. Discussion on how to integrate BioDT with the LifeWatch ERIC infrastructure has already started (see Section 5).

2. Puhuri, HEAppE, and LEXIS Platform integration

Behind each computation in an HPC data centres, there are three main steps:

1. Allocation of resources to specific users;
2. Decision of those users to run a certain computation;
3. Actual execution of the computation, including related data staging operations.

While these general steps are mostly common across all HPC centres, specific details of implementation lead to a situation where treating multiple data centres as a pool of resources from the perspective of digital twin community platforms is extremely difficult.

To address this obstacle, a decision was made to expose a single API for integrating all digital twins and abstract the complexity of allocation, selection and running of computations to a Puhuri service¹, the LEXIS platform and HEAppE middleware².

2.1 Current state

The idea of the integration of the mentioned components is outlined in Figure 1.

Puhuri services provide a tool, covering two corner stones for resource allocation:

- Authentication and Authorization Interface (AAI) based on a reliable digital identity MyAccessID³ that is used consistently across services and HPC sites
- Global project and resource allocation information used by different HPC sites

Such information can also be used by users logged in to LEXIS, to look up and select available computational projects and link them with projects in LEXIS that represent a digital twin. The resource aggregation in LEXIS allows for scenarios where different PIs merge their resources to achieve a common goal.

A manual step that is being automated in a multi-tenant fashion is the setup of a computational environment on the linked service provider in a transparent way, so that access by end-users could be focused on the LEXIS portal and APIs.

Setting up an integrated platform API for digital twins and the development of user-facing functionalities across LEXIS, Puhuri and HEAppE are done in full alignment with the BioDT Technical Platform architecture, involving collaboration between BioDT work packages.

¹ <https://puhuri.io>, a NeIC co-funded service for cross-border resource allocation

² <https://heappe.eu/>, a middleware for exposing in a standard and RESTful manner HPC services of the service provider

³ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/MyAccessID/MyAccessID+Home>, Geant's MyAccessID service

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

Figure 1 – Integration of Puhuri, LEXIS and HEAppE

2.2 Next steps

Requirement scoping and the exposure of new functionalities from Puhuri, LEXIS and HEAppE are being developed based on the progress of integration with community platforms via the R4Lexis package (Section 3).

Work on backchannel communication to increase the integration efficiency (allocations, accounting, membership) among LEXIS, Puhuri, HEAppE and service provider components is expected to be done during the first quarter of 2024, with further adjustments during the year. The backchannel communication is required to provide end users with a responsive and ready to use federated system at the moment of usage.

3. r4lexis package

Given that a significant segment of the BioDT community actively uses the R language, the R package ([r4lexis](#)) has been developed. This package facilitates interaction with the LEXIS platform within the R programming environment, facilitating data transfers, and initiating BioDT workflows. More features of the LEXIS API will be implemented in the future in accordance with the needs of BioDT pDTs.

3.1 LEXIS login

To use the LEXIS Platform, one first needs to be a LEXIS user. Thanks to usage of MyAccessID and B2Connect services which cover a large number of existing authentication services, there is no need for a separate account for most of the users. To interact with the LEXIS API, for example through r4lexis, the user needs to get a token as a means of authentication and authorisation. The authentication token is acquired using the `get_lexis_oauth_token()` function. This function initiates the user login process into the LEXIS Portal (as depicted in Figure 2) and subsequently returns the aforementioned token.

```
> lexis_oauth_token <- get_lexis_oauth_token()
```


Figure 2 – Lexis portal login screen

An authentication token is a list containing information about the token type, its ID and expiration period, and other details. An example of this token is provided below:

```
> lexis_oauth_token
<httr2_token>
token_type: Bearer
access_token: <REDACTED>
expires_at: 2023-10-25 14:24:08
refresh_token: <REDACTED>
refresh_expires_in: 1800
id_token: <REDACTED>
not-before-policy: 1636904877
session_state: c16554ef-dfb9-48bb-8d46-8eeacd0c4c2b
scope: openid exchange-service profile email
```

3.2 Datasets

Using the r4lexis package, one can get information about datasets that are uploaded to the LEXIS platform in specific projects. Each dataset has three stages of access policy:

- Public (can be seen by anyone using the LEXIS Platform)
- Project (visible only to users included in the same project)
- User (visible only to the user who created the dataset)

In r4lexis it is possible to list datasets, list files of the dataset, upload a new dataset, delete a dataset and download a dataset. To list an available dataset, the user can run the `get_dataset_list()` function as follows:

```
> get_dataset_list(lexis_oauth_token, project = "biodt_development")
```

```
Number of datasets: 51
```

```
Datasets:
```

```
[1] Beehave single input
    UUID:    cda1a69c-9c8f-11ed-bb11-fa163e515f81
    Project: biodt_development

[2] Test 2
    UUID:    079b8ab2-a153-11ed-bb11-fa163e515f81
    Project: biodt_development

[3] BioDT BeehaveSingle Test
    UUID:    c611924e-a14d-11ed-bb11-fa163e515f81
    Project: biodt_development

...
```

Each dataset contains information about its name, UUID, which project it is assigned to, owner, encryption, etc:

```
Title:      BioDT BeehaveSingle Test
Project:    biodt_development
Creator:    BioDT BeehaveSingle Test
Owner:
Contributor: BioDT BeehaveSingle Test
Creation Date: 2023-01-31T00:00:00Z
Access Policy: project
Compression: no
Encryption: no
UUID:      c611924e-a14d-11ed-bb11-fa163e515f81
Irods Zone: IT4ILexisZone
```

Using r4lexis, it is also possible to upload (`upload_dataset()`), download (`download_dataset()`) or delete (`delete_dataset()`) individual datasets. Example code for uploading a dataset is provided below:

```
> upload_dataset(file_path = "path_to_file", lexis_oauth_token, metadata)
```

3.3 Workflows

Workflows can be managed in a comparable manner. Here it is important to note that the computational aspect of each pDT is represented as a high level LEXIS workflow (or their combination). Therefore, it is important to have the possibility to list, execute and monitor workflows and workflow executions. By employing the command `get_workflows_list(lexis_oauth_token)`, it is possible to obtain a comprehensive list of all available workflows. Information about a specific workflow can be obtained using the command `get_workflow_info(lexis_oauth_token, workflow_id)`:

```
> get_workflow_info(lexis_oauth_token, "biodt_beehave_karolina")
```

```
$dag_id
[1] "biodt_beehave_karolina"

$default_view
[1] "grid"

$description
[1] "BioDT Beehave Karolina"
```

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

```
$file_token  
[1] "Ii9vcHQvYWlyZmxvdY9kYWdzL2Jpb2R0X2JlZWVhdmVfaXQ0aS5weSI.kepR51tbPJZ4i -  
rhmkocat3haYQ"  
  
$fileloc  
[1] "/opt/airflow/dags/biodt_beehave_it4i.py"  
  
$has_import_errors  
[1] FALSE  
  
...
```

Using the function `get_workflow_default_parameters(lexis_oauth_token, workflow_id)` the parameters of a specific workflow can be obtained.

```
> get_workflow_default_parameters(lexis_oauth_token, "biodt_beehave_karolina")  
  
$access_token  
[1] ""  
  
$biodt_heappe_uri  
[1] "https://heappe.it4i.cz/lexisbiodt"  
  
$cloud_input_path  
[1] "/beehave-input"  
  
$computation_project  
[1] "OPEN-27-31"  
  
$description  
[1] "Beehave HQ Workflow"  
  
$hpc_job_name  
[1] "BioDT Beehave Workflow"  
  
...
```

The `r4lexis` package can also serve the purpose of initiating individual workflows:

```
> execute_workflow(lexis_oauth_token, workflow_id, workflow_parameters, workflow_run_id)  
and verifying their current status:  
> get_workflow_states(lexis_oauth_token, workflow_id)
```

4. Web interface to BioDT

The main way user interaction with BioDT digital twins will be through the Shiny web application. This application is structured in a way where each pDT shares some common basis such as a landing page, workflow execution monitoring and login, as well as featuring pDT-specific modules that can be developed independently from other modules. A major advantage of this application is that even users lacking experience in web app development are able to contribute and edit it, which significantly increases the number of potential collaborators within the field of biodiversity.

4.1 General overview

Currently the application contains several working pages: a landing page, login page, a page for a pDT on pollinator survival (the first use case running on the BioDT Platform), and a computations page. The login page contains some basic information about the project as shown in Figure 3. The login page is a classic login page, where users input their login and password (see Figure 4). This approach will be replaced in the future

with the OAuth redirect authentication flow for getting an access token, which is more secure and flexible. The pollinator survival pDT page and the computations page are shown in Section 4.2.

The Biodiversity Digital Twin prototype will provide advanced models for simulation and prediction capabilities, through practical use cases addressing critical issues related to global biodiversity dynamics.

BioDT exploits the LUMI Supercomputer and employs FAIR data combined with digital infrastructure, predictive modelling and AI solutions, facilitating evidence-based solutions for biodiversity protection and restoration.

The project responds to key EU and international policy initiatives, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, EU Green Deal, UN Sustainable Development Goals, Destination Earth.

Figure 3 – Web application landing page

Login please

Username
mar0486

Password
.....

Login

Login Successful! You can return to work on other pages.

Figure 4 – BioDT web app login screen

From the technical standpoint, the Shiny web app is hosted by the cPouta service provided by CSC (OpenStack virtual machine). For an improved user experience, the Shiny app is containerised and provisioned as one Docker container per user. This is made possible thanks to a framework called [ShinyProxy](#), which runs also as a Docker container. Metrics of usage and individual runs are collected by [Prometheus](#) and supplied to [Grafana](#). Access to the site is made through the [nginx](#) proxy. Currently, the site is not publicly announced as it is still a prototype in development, and it is impossible to use it without guidance.

The connection between the Shiny app and LEXIS is always made through the `r4lexis` package, made convenient by both the app and `r4lexis` package relying on the R language. The greatest downside of using the LEXIS DDI or other research infrastructure repositories (such as [GBIF](#) for data storage is that, before the user can see the data themselves, they need to be transferred to the Shiny app. This takes time and reduces user comfort. However, it is impossible to have all the possible data used in the Shiny app mirrored on the OpenStack virtual machine. The process of communication between the Shiny app and LEXIS, as well as the communication process between the BioDT infrastructure cloud and HPC partitions with LEXIS DDI, are outlined in Figure 5. In practice, communication with the LEXIS DDI can be replaced by communication with any other data storage. The biggest advantage of using the LEXIS DDI is the communication speed between the BioDT infrastructure and the LEXIS DDI, since they are usually at the same centre (unlike other storage solutions).

Figure 5 – Interaction between the Shiny web app and BioDT infrastructure

4.2 Prototype digital twin of pollinator survival

The pollinator survival pDT page is a relatively simple page which consists of three blocks showing input data: an input map, a lookup table and a parameter table. Input maps and lookup tables are currently stored in a special dataset in the LEXIS DDI and need to be downloaded before they can be showed. Users have the possibility to choose which map and lookup table they want to use and then download them. Values in the lookup table and parameter table may be edited before the workflow is executed. Additionally, users need to upload a special dbf file containing coordinates of locations for which the computation should be made. When this is done, they can execute the workflow. All the data are then compressed and uploaded to the LEXIS DDI as a new dataset and used as an input for the workflow execution. This process should be improved in future versions as it is not needed to create new datasets for maps, lookup tables, and parameter settings that were used before. A screenshot of part of the pollinator pDT page is shown in Figure 6.

Once the workflow is executed, users are able to check the status of the workflow by going to the computations tab. Here they can select for which pDT they want to show workflows and obtain a coarse status overview of the workflow, which can be: Running, Failed or Success (see Figure 7). While it would be possible to provide much more fine-grained status information within the currently running task in the workflow, this could cause confusion because expected users of the Shiny web app will have little knowledge about the underlying BioDT infrastructure and details of the workflows. To inform future design choices concerning BioDT interface development and to account for user feedback, several features of the Shiny web app will be discussed with users at hackathon events planned as part of the project and as part of pDT presentations delivered to users.

Figure 6 – Pollinator survival pDT web GUI

Figure 7 – Workflow status page

5. LifeWatch ERIC Tesseract integration

Communication with the LifeWatch ERIC infrastructure team has been established to discuss the possibility of integrating BioDT prototype digital twins into the LifeWatch ERIC services. While this effort is at an early stage, using a BioDT REST API is being pursued as the most suitable way of integration. The motivation underlying this work is to enable the execution of BioDT digital twin computations as part of workflows created in the LifeWatch ERIC platform.

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

6. Next steps

Current efforts will be distributed mostly into three development areas:

- 🔥 Construction Shiny web application modules for each of the pDTs.
- 🔥 Updating the authentication flow for the Shiny web application to use OAuth redirecting instead of a password and username.
- 🔥 LifeWatch infrastructure integration.

In addition, work on Puhuri, HEAppE, and LEXIS integration is planned to continue, with work also focused on identifying other possible platforms where BioDT could be integrated. A further key activity pursued within the project involves integration with Destination Earth.